

Report to the SBAH Baghdad on the Survey Season in Spring 2025 of the Rural Babylonia (RuBab) Project (Version 2.0)

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1 Introduction

The planning of the Spring Season 2025 was a bit difficult because two team members were not allowed by their universities to come to southern Iraq (Mark Altaweel and Kourosh Mohammadkhani, the latter was allowed in the end to come for the last week of the work). Therefore, the core team constituted Bernhard Schneider (field director), Ali Tubr Al-Guburi (surveyor, drone) and Kourosh Mohammadkhani. The team had the luck to count on the support by three motivated young colleagues from SBAH Diwaniyah: Achmed Ali Jassim, Haider Kamel Jassim, and Hassan Jabbar Kazim. Each of them helped to bring the first official survey season to a successful end. We hope we can integrate all of them again during the next Season of the RuBab (Rural Babylonia) Project in our future campaigns.

The limitation of urban centers like Nippur on local events makes it necessary to intensify the survey coverage of the 2nd and 1st millennium BC sites in the project region (Fig. 1). With few exceptions the Northern and Southwestern survey sector was covered during the Spring Season 2025.

Fig. 1: RuBab (Rural Babylonia) Survey Area (split in three survey zones of access: North/Southwest/Southeast).

2 Methodology

The sites were visited (see 3.1.1 below) and prospected with drone photography (DJI Phantom 4 Pro) including benchmarks measured with differential GPS/GNSS system. With the collected raw material, georeferenced orthophotos will be produced. Other drone systems were utilized such as DJI Mavic Mini 4 Pro and Autel Evo II V3 640T (thermography, see 6. below). Only very focused and limited sherd collection was conducted, as the area was already heavily surveyed by the QADIS survey team in the 2010s, sometimes resulting in very sparse pottery left at certain sites. In the case of Ishan Hâfudh, even the pottery which was left on the surface of the site in 2024 was collected by somebody of the antiquities department. In other instances, limited sherd collection was conducted when recent looting was encountered (see 5. below).

Remarks concerning the dating of a site's occupation

The basis of this survey is the documentation provided by Robert McCormick Adams (1981) as well as the publications of the QADIS survey team (Marchetti et al 2018; idem. 2020 etc.) inclusive the accessible online GIS platform *floodplains*.¹ In the instances of newly discovered sites (Rb01, Fig. 3 and Rb02), the surface pottery sherds and other objects encountered are taken as the main evidence (see Rb01: Fig. 3 to Fig. 4 and Rb02 Fig. 5 to Fig. 9).

Site deposition of collected pottery and objects found

Near the end of the season, while trying to organize the transport of objects to the Museum in Baghdad, we were informed by the head of the SBAH branch in Diwaniyah that all the collected pottery as well as the objects (see 4. Finds, below) had to be redeposited at the sites of origin. Therefore, from this moment on, no pottery was collected by the RuBab survey team at all (also not from Rb02). It is therefore hoped that the expedition will be allowed to bring the objects found directly to the Iraqi Museum in Baghdad as it is done by other teams in future campaigns.

The time-consuming task to transport and rebury pottery all over the survey region also prevented the planned work of pottery drawings for Rb01 and other sites which will be done in the framework of the Autumn 2025 campaign by the RuBab survey.

3. Preliminary Results

3.1. Drone Surveying and Ground Truthing²

The framework for the Spring 2025 campaign was set to take care of the most important rural sites in the Survey region with Neo-Babylonian until Parthian occupation.

3.1.1 Sites visited

The sites visited and mostly documented via drone survey were: Tell el-Laham 1230-31, Tell Abu Qubur 1235, Tell Semeh el-Jenubi 1236, Ishan Hâfudh/Hayayah Qd 63a-b+d, Ishan Hâfudh/Ishan Joħa Qd 63c, Tell Sowaleh, Tell ‘Aqbi 1352, H1180, Qd 41 Ishan Abu Jāwan, Qd 42, Qd 44 “Ishan Said Abbas”, Qd 55 “Ishan Ĥraymsāt”, Tell el-Fakhar 1090-91, 1095, Tell al-Ĥraymsāt 1244-45, Tell Abu Tuabit 1251 (Fig. 2), Tell Abu Jāwan 985, Tell Gamel 989, Tell Abu-Jawarir 1127, 978, Tell Abyad 1081, 1002, 1003, Rb 01, Rb 02, Tell Dhahāyah/Dhahīya 1270 and 1272-73, 1025. Furthermore, Ishan Sellab (see below) was visited.

¹ <https://floodplains.orientlab.net/> last access 13 November 2025. See also Marchetti et al. 2023.

² All site numbers are provided according to Adams 1981 and Marchetti et al 2017, 2018, 2020. New sites are numbered according to the designation Rb (Rural Babylonia) and double-digit number like Rb 01.

Tell Abu Tuabit (Adams 1981: No. 1251):

Heavy looting up to 2,5-3 m deep rectangular trenches brought on the surface potentially earlier occupation layers before the main erosional surface layers which date to the Late Parthian period, around ca. 150-250 AD (compare Nippur Mound III “Parthian Fortress”). Therefore, a collection of diagnostic sherds was collected, with the mound separated in West/Central/East sector. As in the agricultural fields to the southwest of the site, here on the main mound a diagnostic “Kassite goblet” fragment could be collected (Fig. 2). This adds another occupation period to this site and is proof of human activity during at least part of the Late Bronze Age (for the latter see also Adams 1981: No. 1249-50).

Fig. 2: Pottery collection (mainly Parthian period) from Western sector of main mound of Tell Tuabit (Adams 1981: No. 1251). One example of Kassite goblet was encountered in this part of the site with further examples in the fields to the Southwest of the site. Project RuBab, Spring 2025.

3.1.3 Sites relocated

Adams' site 1003 could be relocated (UTM 38 S 527942.00 m E, 3546049.00 m N) towards ca. 450 m to the West of its current position.

3.1.4 Sites newly discovered

The two newly discovered sites are

- Rb01 (UTM 38 S 545587.00 m E, 3543433.00 m N, size ca. 0.5 ha) and

Rb01 is a small *Ishan* of the Late Sasanian/Early Islamic period, probably also settled during the Middle Islamic period (). It is situated along a paleochannel running from Northwest to Southeast (Fig. 3), situated on the highest point of an ancient levée.

Fig. 3: Orthophoto of „New Ishan“ Rb01 (in Southwest) and the traces of a paleochannel (NW-SE) in the fields to the Northeast. Project RuBab, Spring 2025.

New Ishan Rb01

Fig. 4: Glazed and decorated sherds from Rb01 New Ishan. Project RuBab, Spring 2025.

- Rb02 (UTM 38 S 557757.00 m E, 3548667.00 m N, size ca. 10 ha).

Approximately to the same period as Rb01 dates Rb02 (Fig. 5) which likely was a planned extension with a grid of canals from the neighboring site of Tell Dhahīya (Adams 1981: No. 1273). It probably constitutes a Western extension of the ancient settlement core at Dhahīya, excavated (unpublished) during the work related to the construction of the Southern outlet of Hawr Dalmaj in the framework of the “Third River” drain project.³ No sherd collection was taken from Rb02 but examples on the surface provided a clear picture of the sites periods of occupation which dating mainly into the Sasanian period with probable continuity into the Early Islamic period (Fig. 7-Fig. 9).

³ I would be very interested in publishing the available documentation of the Dhahīya excavations, if the SBAH desires.

Fig. 5: Orthophoto of Rb02, situated West of the Dalmaj outlet drain and Tell Dahayah. Project Rubab, Spring 2025.

Fig. 6: Detail of northeastern part of Rb02. Project Rubab, Spring 2025.

Fig. 7: Samples of glazed and decorated ceramic sherds on surface of Rb02. Project RuBab, Spring 2025.

Fig. 8: Rim fragment of a glass bottle. On surface of northeastern part of Rb02. Project RuBab, Spring 2025.

Fig. 9: Overview of assemblage of brick fragments on surface of Rb02. Project RuBab, Spring 2025.

4. Finds

At the request of the SBAH Diwaniyah all the collected pottery and objects were reburied at the sites of origin.

4.1 Summary

Several fragmentary terracotta animal figures (including riders) were found mainly at Ishan Ḥraymsāt (Qd 55), Ishan Said Abbas (Qd 44) and Tell el-Laham (Adams 1981: No. 1230).

The fragments of several stamped bricks with a Nebuchadnezzar standard inscription (where preserved to judge the variety) were found at Tell Abu Qubur (Adams 1981: No. 1235). One nearly complete brick of the same variety, inclusive the fragment of another (Sumerian?) inscription was found at Tell Abu Jāwan (Adams 1981: No. 985).

Bronze/Copper fragments were found at Tell el-Fakhar (Adams 1981: No. 1090) besides looters pits (one horse tooth fragment was encountered on-site). They were probably horse bridles (one

nearly complete, shaped like an elongated eight). A frit bead was found in a caterpillar trench into the neighboring lower mound (Adams 1981: No. 1091).

4.2 Listing of most important finds (site: description):

- “Ishan Ḥraymsāt” Qd 55/1 (Fig. 10): A fragmentary terracotta “horse-and-rider” figure (horse without head preserved); other fragments of terracotta animal figures of mostly horses (Fig. 12), sickle fragment (Fig. 12, above). For the continued use of terracotta sickle blades until at least the beginning of the 2nd millennium BCE see the results of the QADIS survey (Marchetti et al 2020: 185-186). Concerning pottery from “Ishan Ḥraymsāt” Qd 55/2, deriving from a looted context (ca. before 2010), is the fragment of a large vessel with a hole in the bottom (funneled vessel, Fig. 14), known to be used for production of beer (Paulette 2024: 126-135). A similar vessel was found in burial context at Nippur, dug there from “Post-Level I” into Level III of “Tablet Hill” (TA) by the Joint expedition of Philadelphia and Chicago 1948-52 (McCown and Haines 1967, Pl. 157:15) and therefore dating approximately to the Seleucid period (ca. 150 BCE). The exact context at Ishan Ḥraymsāt needs to be further studied on-site. The first impression was that it derived from a burial context, disturbed by the looters. It could be as well have been in situ evidence of rural beer brewing in the agricultural hinterland of the region, dating sometime after the Neo-Babylonian period.

Fig. 10: Orthophoto of Ishan Ḥraymsāt (Qd55). Project Rubab, Spring 2025.

Fig. 11: Detail of Ishan Hraymsāt with findspots indicated [squares]. Project RuBab, Spring 2025.

Fig. 12: Terracotta objects from Ishan Hraymsāt. Project RuBab, Spring 2025.

Fig. 13: Fragmentary horse-and-rider figure from Ishan Hraymsāt (above). Details (below). Project Rubab, Spring 2025.

Fig. 14: Above: Fragment from the body of the funneled vessel from Ishan Hraymsat. Below. Rounded base of funneled vessel.

- “Ishan Said Abbas” Qd 44/1 (Fig. 16-Fig. 17): A “horse-and-rider” terracotta figure fragment (part of torso with rider) was found beside a recent looting pit.

Fig. 15: Map with Orthophoto of Ishan Said Abbas (Qd44) and findspot (square) of indicated. Project Rubab, Spring 2025.

Fig. 16: “Ishan Said Abbas” Qd 44/1, horse-and-rider figure fragment (views from right, left, above). Project Rubab, Spring 2025.

- Tell Abu Jawan 985/1 (Fig. 18): Neo-Babylonian stamped inscription of Nebuchadnezzar II (605-562 BC) on greenish deformed brick fragment (28x22x6 cm) showing traces of secondary firing on lower flat side (Fig. 18: right) and 985/2 a small fragment of a stamped brick with inscription (Sumerian?), probably of Ur III/Isin date (Fig. 18).

Fig. 17: Tell Abu Jawan 985/1, fragmentary brick with traces of Neo-Babylonian stamped standard inscription of Nebuchadnezzar II (605-562 BC), showing traces of secondary firing. Project Rubab, Spring 2025.

Fig. 18: 985/2 a small fragment (16 x 12 6 cm) of a yellowish-brown stamped brick with inscription (Sumerian?), probably of Ur III/Isin date. Project Rubab, Spring 2025.

- Tell Abu Qubur 1235: several fragments of Neo-Babylonian stamped inscription (Fig. 20) of Nebuchadnezzar II (605-562 BC) showing traces of secondary burning (Fig. 22), kept *in situ*. As an example with cuneiform characters still visible, see Fig. 21. A more complete brick, preserved in several fragments, shows no visible traces of secondary firing (Fig. 20).

Fig. 19: Orthophoto of Tell Abu Qubur (with findspots of basalt, stamped brick fragments, brick slag) and Tell Semeh.

Fig. 20: Example of a better preserved stamped brick with faint traces of an inscription of Nebuchadnezzar II on surface of Tell Abu Qubur. Project RuBab, Spring 2025.

Fig. 21: Example of a melted brick with rest of the inscription still readable (left). Detail of fragmentary inscription (middle). Transliteration of visible rests of inscription (right).

Fig. 22: Examples of Neo-Babylonian bricks with secondary firing on surface of Tell Abu Qubur. Project RuBab, Spring 2025.

- Tell el-Fakhar 1090/1 (Fig. 23): Beside earlier looters trenches were found a bronze/copper object (shaped like 8) probably belonging to horse bridle (?) and several fragments of similar objects nearby looters pits. A flake of a horse tooth beside it strengthens the connection towards an implement belonging to a horse or donkey (Fig. 23). Although no comparable object could be found in other excavation reports (Babylon, Uruk, Isin, Nippur), the University of Pennsylvania Museum of Archaeology

and Anthropology in Philadelphia stores fragments of a similar object from the early Nippur expeditions of 1889-1900!⁴ The object was made of a single piece of a metal rod, bended on both ends inward towards the center in antiquity and fixed with a metal rivet or nail (see *Fig. 23*: right) at the interconnection.

- Tell el-Fakhar 1091/1: Frit bead (turquoise color) at bulldozer cut.

Fig. 23: Metal (copper/bronze) object Tell el-Fakhar 1090/1 (left) and fragments Tell el-Fakhar 1090/2 (center) and Tell el-Fakhar 1090/3 (right). Project Rubab, Spring 2025.

Fig. 24: Metal (copper/bronze) object. Project RuBab, Spring 2025.

Fig. 25: Tell el-Fakhar 1091/1. Project RuBab, Spring 2025.

⁴ See online collection <https://www.penn.museum/collections/>, accessed 13 November 2025.

- “New Ishan” Rb01: Bronze axe/chisel, 2,1 x 4,5 cm (Fig. 26).

Fig. 26: Bronze axe or chisel from Rb01. Project RuBab, Spring 2025.

- Tell Abu Tuabit (Adams 1981: No. 1251): several fragments of a bezel from a metal ring (Fig. 27) and a fragment of an incense burner (Fig. 28) from Parthian period.

Fig. 27: Fragment (bezel) of a metal ring. Tell Abu Tuabit (Adams 1981: No. 1251).

Fig. 28: Fragment of an incense burner from Parthian period. Tell Abu Tuabit. Project RuBab, Spring 2025.

- Tell el-Laham 1230/1: spout of a vessel in shape of a calf; 1230/2 fragments of a horse animal figure. The recent excavations at Seleucia brought to light similar fragments.

Fig. 29: Fragmentary spout of a ceramic vessel in the form of a calf. Project RuBab, Spring 2025.

- Ishan Hâfudh NW, disturbed area: Already in 2024 were found two objects at the disturbed part of the site: in a heap of sorted out broken bricks was found a terracotta relief fragment (4,2x3,8 cm) with part of torso and right arm preserved (Fig. 30: left), showing a bearded (beard broken) god with two long locks holding an object in hands. Furthermore, (Fig. 30: right) at the slope of the disturbed area was found a cylinder seal (3,8 x 1,5 diam., bone) made of bone, showing an introductory scene with a throning goddess wearing a flounced robe. This scene is datable roughly into the Ur III to Isin-Larsa period. Further conclusions are not possible because of the eroded state of the object.

Fig. 30: Left: Fragmentary terracotta relief with part of torso preserved, showing a bearded god with two long locks holding an object (vessel) in hands. Also visible is the vertical groove which serves as separator of the scene when rolled out. From disturbed area of Ishan Hâfudh NW, lying together with sieved brick fragments. Right: from slope at point of disturbed area of Ishan Hâfudh NW.

5. Looting as an ongoing problem goes new devastating ways:

Faster, more technical, more mobile looting!

The pace of looting has regained magnitude. Whereas in 2024 only occasional looting was encountered, this year, multiple visits of several sites proofed the ongoing looting of sites over several weeks. Also, the obvious use of technology, such as metal detectors (spade deep pits, sometimes with traces of copper/bronze still visible) but probably also other non-invasive technologies (cavity detectors etc.) are in use as is shown by the looting of relatively deep (ca. 2-2.5 m) buried sarcophagi. *This should also concern a change of the strategy of site protection without any active mobile (regionally operating) site guards.*

5.1 Some documented case studies

Tell Abu Tuabit 1251:

Looted Parthian slipper coffin fragments gave ample indication that since Spring 2024 new looting activity took place. Although, some of the coffins are situated nearby the surface, one unglazed version of a slipper coffin (Fig. 31) in a rectangle N-S oriented “archaeological trench” was still stuck in the N-section of the trench (2-2.5 m deep).

Fig. 31: Looters trench (North-South) with unglazed slipper coffin at Abu-Tuabit 1251. View towards North. Project Rubab, Spring 2025.

Ishan Hâfudh/Hayāyah (NE mound) Qd 63a

A 50 cm deep looting pit was encountered while walking over the NE mound.

Ishan Hâfudh/Hayāyah (SE mound) Qd 63b

Shallow pits on the surface are the result of the removal of benchmarks by unknown individuals. All the surface pottery documented in 2024 has disappeared!

Tell ‘Aqbi (Adams 1981: No. 1352)

Sometime before 3rd February 2024 (*terminus post quem* 28 March 2021) a rectangular trench resembling an “archaeological” deep sounding), ca. 2-2.5 m deep was cut into the Southern part of Tell ‘Aqbi. It was cut through a massive mud brick structure. Since it was cut it was intentionally reburied. Therefore the total depth of destruction is unclear.

Fig. 32: Rectangular trench (N-S) at the southern part of Tell 'Aqbi. View towards North. Project Rubab, Spring 2025.

(Ishan) Sellab (38 R 533365.21 m E, 3533718.43 m N)

Islamic period burials looted with human bones and skulls still freshly lying around, disturbed ca. within the last year.

Fig. 33: Most recent looting at Ishan Sellab with fragments of a human skull visible (after 3 February 2024). Project Rubab, Spring 2025.

5.2 Metal detecting as a new phenomenon:

H1244-45 Tell al-Hraymsāt and “Ishan Hraymsāt” Qd 55

The remains left by a metal detectorist were documented by us over several days to make 20+ shovel deep pits, on two different days within three days on Tell al-Hraymsāt (Adams 1981: 1244-45). Also, the above-mentioned funneled vessel fell victim to more recent looting.

On one occasion at Qd 55, even bronze flakes could be seen left on the site of a fleshly looted burial (Fig. 35). This was an indication for an active metal detectorist in this part of the survey region

Fig. 34: Looted funneled vessel with earlier looting pit in foreground. Ishan Hraymsat. Project RuBab, Spring 2025.

Fig. 35: Freshly looted burial at Ishan Ḥraymsāt. Project Rubab, Spring 2025.

Tell al-Laham (Adams 1981: No. 1230)

Also, here metal detectorists are searching for detectable precious objects (probably coins, fibulae, needles etc.) to be dug out easily with a common shovel (Fig. 36).

Fig. 36: Recent small-scale looting by metal detectorists at Tell al-Laham. As scale serves here the breath of a usual shovel. Project Rubab, Spring 2025.

5.3 Summary

Bulldozing and other activities of farmers encroachment are an ongoing concern but the new development of metal detectorists is very concerning as it will be another layer of destruction without any pattern recognizable concerning preference in occupation. Another problem is driving with 4x4 cars (Adams 1982: No .1235 “Tell Abu Qubur”) or tractors (Tell Sowaleh) on water soaked, muddy mounds after heavy rainfall. The fact that such sites are sometimes simply called “heights” by the locals shows that they are not even recognized as such shows that information is not spread well in the rural parts of the area.

5.4 Immediate measurements of site protection and creating awareness in the local community

As it is not foreseeable that a real guard who frequently visits the sites⁵ would be hired soon, more cost neutral measurements are suggested. Here it would suffice to create awareness within the communities who live beside sites on a regular basis (annually, or in a two-year rhythm). A suggestion here would be to send school classes to visit ongoing excavations and other research programs. With the help of the people sent by the SBAH we could easily lead them through sites and show part of our work.

6. Use of new technologies in Surveying:

Identifying Mudbrick Walls via Drone (UAV) Thermography at Tell al-Laham

Bernhard Schneider, Ali Tubr Al-Guburi

During the fieldwork season in Spring 2025 we had the opportunity to test a new drone quadcopter (UAV= Unmanned Aerial Vehicle) Autel Evo II 640T V3 with a FLIR camera with a 640x512 standard resolution. Already during the first exploration flight at the ancient site of Tell al-Laham⁶ (Adams 1981: No. 1230-31) we could experience the powerful potential of this kind of aerial prospection in our Survey region (project RuBab) within the ‘Afak district in the eastern part of Al-Qadisiyah province in Southern Iraq. This note is an outcome of these explorations which identified an otherwise unrecognizable mudbrick wall on a sunny day around noon, just a day after heavier rainfall in the region.

Therefore, an altitude of 100 m (Fig. 37) was chosen to survey the immediate environs of Tell el-Laham. Further depth was reached in the thermal image to get a maximum out of the thermal camera within the maximum recommended range as provided by the producer of 15 m distance (Fig. 38).

⁵ In 2024 Ali Shalgham was informed about the renewed looting activity and also the need to re-hire a guard in the region around ‘Afak was discussed.

⁶ Probably to be identified with the ancient Sumerian city of Larak (See Marchetti et al 2018; 2020?).

Fig. 37: Multispectral (Autel Evo II V3) drone images produced from 100 m height.

Fig. 38: Multispectral (Autel Evo II V3) drone images produced from 15 m height.

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